

10.5281/zenodo.11667924

Vol. 07 Issue 05 May - 2024

Manuscript ID: #01402

OVERVIEW OF THE ROLE OF THE VILLAGE CONSULTATIVE BOARD IN VILLAGE GOVERNMENT CASE STUDY IN SUNGAI PAYANG VILLAGE, LOA KULU SUBDISTRICT, KUTAI KARTANEGARA REGENCY

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Abstract

Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages has brought new enthusiasm and hope to create independent villages. The Law regulates the position, function and role of village government, and also explains the representation of the population with the formation of the Regional Consultative Board (BPD). BPD has a strategic function in determining village policies and supervising the implementation of village government. The aim of the research is to determine the role and supporting and inhibiting factors related to the performance of the BPD of Sungai Payang Village, Loa Kulu District, Kutai Kartanegara Regency. This qualitative descriptive research was carried out in Sungai Payang Village, Loa Kulu District, Kutai Kartanegara Regency from February to May 2023. Key informants and informants who were the subjects of the research were: Village Head, Chair of the BPD, Chair of the Empowerment Institution Community, Chair of Traditional Institutions, Youth Leaders, and Women Leaders. Data collection was carried out through library research obtained through journals, books or supporting materials in research; and through field research through observation, interviews, and documentation. Data analysis was carried out by systematically searching and compiling data obtained from interviews, observations and documentation. The stages of data analysis are: data collection, data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions/verification. The results of the research show that: (1) BPD Sungai Payang has carried out its role well as supervisor of village development, supervisor of Village Head performance, supervisor of village finances, exploring, accommodating and channeling community aspirations, and submitting Draft Village Regulations; (2) supporting factors for BPD Sungai Payang activities are that the BPD administrators are on average educated, the availability of a BPD office, BPD members understand the problems, potential and conditions of the village, and understand the rules related to the technical implementation of village government, and the creation of good cooperation between BPD and Village Government; and (3) factors inhibiting the tasks and role of the BPD, namely: lack of coordination between institutions and village officials to absorb the aspirations of village residents, sometimes personal egos and certain groups emerge, some BPD administrators have junior high school education, not all BPD members are able to understand the main duties & position of the BPD, and there is a lack of synchronization between the BPD and the village government in terms of the village development budget.

Keywords:

Role, Supporting and Inhibiting Factors, Village Consultative Board.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Since the issuance of the decision on Regional Autonomy, its implementation will depend greatly on the readiness of regional governments to organize and implement regional government systems to create community development in the administration of government.

Even though the Republic of Indonesia adheres to the principle of a unitary state with the center of power in the central government, due to the diversity of the Indonesian nation in terms of social, cultural, economic, religious, linguistic, ethnic, and educational levels of society, the distribution of power/authority (decentralization) needs to be channeled to autonomous regions (Kaloh, 2007). The formation of autonomous regions will not cause national disintegration, but will instead be conducive to achieving national integration (Rosa and Arliman, 2017).

The diverse regional conditions need to be addressed realistically to increase village benefits by increasing the quality and quantity of infrastructure that is more contributive to regional/village economic growth.

In Law no. 6 of 2014 concerning Villages, Article 1 paragraph 1 states that villages are villages and traditional villages or referred to by other names, hereinafter referred to as Villages, are legal community units that have territorial boundaries that have the authority to regulate and manage government affairs, the interests of local communities based on community initiatives, rights of origin, and/or traditional rights that are recognized and respected in the government system of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. The issuance of the Village Law brings new enthusiasm and hope to create independent villages, where all the needs and interests of village communities can be better accommodated.

The importance of village development needs to receive attention from the government so that development can be carried out according to the needs and aspirations of local communities. On the other hand, the importance of village development must be carried out so that there is no imbalance in development between rural and urban development, apart from that, it is also to suppress urbanization, population movement from villages to cities with the hope that the population will not only be concentrated in cities.

One measure of the success of village development is the extent to which community members can play a role in the development of the village to ensure that the results of development, both physical and non-physical, can be enjoyed by the community and there is a sense of local community ownership of the success of village development. The implementation of village development must be supported by community participation to empower the community, so that they can solve the problems they face themselves, through partnerships, transparency, equality, and responsibility. To accommodate the wishes of the community in development, a bottom-up planning system is used, a term which is participatory planning. The lowest stage is the coordination meeting (Suparman, 2010).

The need for community involvement is considered very important because development that places too much emphasis on the role of bureaucratic government (characterized by the government down to down) has received sharp criticism, which is less sensitive to local needs. Apart from that, the implementation of development that prioritizes the community in implementing development programs, means providing the widest possible opportunity for the community to direct resources, and potential, plan and make decisions, and evaluate development activities that will improve their welfare so that they are empowered.

In Law Number 23 of 2014, it is stated that within the Village Government, two bodies are separate from each other, namely the Executive Body consisting of the Village Head, along with other Village officials, and the Legislative Body which is played by the Village Consultative Board (BPD). These two bodies are the government. Villages that organize autonomous regional village government. In carrying out his duties and obligations, the Village Head is responsible to the people

through the Village Consultative Board (BPD) and is obliged to submit reports regarding the implementation of his duties to the Regent.

Puasah et al (2022) stated that the success of development in the Village is not only the absolute responsibility of the Village Government but also requires the role of all stakeholders in the village. Successful development in a village must be carried out by all levels of society, community groups, and institutions in the village, one of which is the Village Consultative Body (BPD).

In the Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia (Permendagri RI) Number 110 of 2016, the Village Consultative Board has now been implemented in all villages in Indonesia. The BPD has strategic functions in determining village policies and supervision, namely: (1) discussing and agreeing on draft village regulations with the village head; (2) accommodating and channeling the aspirations of the village community, and (3) supervising the performance of the village head (Village Law Article 55).

Based on the description above, it is necessary to carry out a study that aims to determine the role and supporting and inhibiting factors related to the performance of the Village Consultative Body (BPD) of Sungai Payang Village, Loa Kulu District, Kutai Kartanegara Regency.

2. BASIC THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. The Role of BPD in Village Development

According to Soerjono (2012), that role is a dynamic aspect of position (status). If someone carries out their rights and obligations by their position, they are carrying out a role. Role is a dynamic aspect of life (status), if someone carries out their rights and obligations by their position, then they are carrying out a role. According to Alberto (2014), a role can be defined as behavior that is regulated and expected from someone in a certain position. Leaders in an organization have roles, each job carries expectations for how the person holding the role will behave. The fact that organizations identify the work to be done and the desired role behavior that goes along with the work also means that expectations regarding “roles” are very important in regulating subordinate behavior.

According to Rivai (2006), a role is a form of behavior that is regulated and expected from someone in a certain position. Roles have several concepts, namely: dynamic aspects of position, set of rights and obligations. the actual behavior of the position holder, and the part of the activity performed by the person. The types or forms of roles are divided into three, namely as follows:

- a. An active role is a role given by group members because of their position in the group as group activists, such as administrators, officials, and so on.
- b. A participatory role is a role given by group members in general to their group, this kind of member participation will make a very useful contribution to the group itself.
- c. A passive role is a passive contribution by group members, where group members refrain from giving themselves the opportunity for other functions in the group to run well.

According to Soekanto (2012), there are several dimensions related to roles, described as follows:

- a. Role as a policy; Adherents of this understanding argue that a role is a policy that is appropriate and well implemented.
- b. Role as strategy; Adherents of this understanding maintain that roles are a strategy to gain support from society (public support). This opinion is based on an understanding that if a decision is well documented, then the decision has credibility.
- c. Role as a communication tool; Roles are utilized as instruments or tools to obtain input in the form of information in the decision-making process.
- d. Role as a dispute resolution tool; Roles are utilized as a way to reduce and reduce conflict through efforts to achieve consensus on existing opinions. The assumption underlying this

perception is that exchanging ideas and views can increase understanding and tolerance and reduce feelings of mistrust and confusion.

- e. Role as therapy; According to this perception, the role is carried out as an effort to "treat" psychological problems such as feelings of powerlessness, lack of self-confidence, and the feeling that they are not an important component in a group.

About the role of the Village Consultative Body (BPD) in implementing development, as stated in the Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia (Permendagri RI) Number 110 of 2016 concerning the role of the Village Consultative Body (BPD), namely: (1) As supervisor of village development activities; (2) As supervisor of the performance of the village head. As supervisor of village financial management; (3) Monitoring and evaluating development activities in the village; (4) Accommodating and channeling the aspirations of village residents; (5) Submitting draft village regulations and their authority; and (6) Expressing the right to suggestions and opinions to the Village Head.

2.2. Goals of Arrangement and Membership of the Village Consultative Body

The objectives of regulating the Village Consultative Body (BPD) in the Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia (Permendagri RI) Number 110 of 2016 concerning the Village Consultative Body are: (1) to emphasize the BPD in the administration of Village Government, and (2) encourage BPD to be able to accommodate; and encourage BPD to realize good governance.

Membership of the Village Consultative Body (BPD) consists of:

1. BPD members are representatives of the village population based on regional representation and women's representation, whose filling is carried out democratically through a direct election process or representative deliberation
2. The number of BPD members as referred to in the paragraph is determined with an odd number, at least 5 (five) people and a maximum of 9 (nine) people
3. Determination of the number of BPD members as referred to in the paragraph takes into account the population and the financial capacity of the Village.
4. The area as intended in paragraph (1) is an area within a village such as a hamlet, RW, or RT area.

The institutional and composition of the Village Consultative Body (BPD) consists of:

1. The BPD institution consists of:
 - a. leader; And
 - b. field.
2. The leadership of the BPD as intended consists of:
 - a. 1 (one) chairman;
 - b. 1 (one) deputy chairman; and 1 (one) secretary
3. The fields as intended in paragraph (1) letter b consist of:
 - a. In the field of Village Government administration and community development; And
 - b. In the field of Village development and empowerment of Village communities

Description of the Rights, Obligations, and Authorities of the Village Consultative Body (BPD), namely: BPD has the right to:

1. Supervise and request information regarding the implementation of Village Government from the Village Government;
2. Express opinions on the implementation of Village Government, implementation of Village development, development of Village society, and empowerment of Village communities; and

3. Obtain operational costs for carrying out their duties and functions from the Village Revenue and Expenditure Budget

Description of the Rights of Members of the Village Consultative Body (BPD), namely:

1. BPD members have the right to:
 - a. Submit a proposal for a draft Village Regulation;
 - b. Asking question;
 - c. Convey suggestions and/or opinions;
 - d. Choose and be chosen; and
 - e. receive allowances from the Revenue and Expenditure Budget Village.
2. The rights of BPD members as referred to in paragraphs A to D are used in BPD deliberations. In addition to the rights as intended in paragraph (1), BPD has the right to:
 - a. Obtain capacity development through education and training, outreach, technical guidance, and field visits conducted within the country; and
 - b. Awards from the Government, Provincial Government, and Regency/City Government for outstanding BPD leaders and members.

Description of Obligations of Village Consultative Body (BPD) Members, namely :

1. Upholding and practicing Pancasila, implementing the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, as well as maintaining and maintaining the integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia and Bhinneka Tunggal Ika;
2. Implementing democratic life with gender equality in the implementation of the One Government;
3. Prioritize public interests above personal, group, and/or group interests;
4. Respect the socio-cultural values and customs of the Village community;
5. maintain norms and ethics in working relationships with Village Government institutions and other village institutions; And
6. guarding community aspirations, maintaining the authority and stability of Village Government administration, and pioneering Village Government administration based on good governance.

Authority of the Village Consultative Body (BPD), namely :

1. Holding meetings with the community to obtain aspirations;
2. Convey community aspirations to the Village Government verbally and in writing;
3. Submit draft Village Regulations which fall under its authority;
4. Carry out monitoring and evaluation of the Village Head's performance;
5. Request information regarding the implementation of Village Government from the Village Government;
6. Express opinions on the implementation of Village Government, implementation of Village development, development of Village society, and empowerment of Village communities;
7. Guarding community aspirations, maintaining the authority and stability of Village Government administration, and pioneering Village Government administration based on good governance;
8. Prepare BPD rules and regulations;
9. Submit incidental monitoring results reports to the Regent/Mayor via the sub-district head;
10. Prepare and submit a written proposal for a BPD operational cost plan to the Village Head to be allocated in the Village Budget and Revenue and Expenditure Draft;
11. Manage BPD operational costs;
12. Proposing the formation of a Village Inter-Institutional Communication Forum to the Village Head; and Conducting visits to the community in the context of monitoring and evaluating the implementation of village government.

Funding for the implementation of BPD activities is borne by:

1. Provincial Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget;
2. Regency/City Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget;
3. Village Revenue and Expenditure Budget; And
4. Other sources that are valid and non-binding.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

3.1. Location and Time

The research was carried out in Sungai Payang Village, Loa Kulu District, Kutai Kartanegara Regency from February to May 2023.

3.2. Types of research

This research is a qualitative descriptive study that aims to collect detailed actual information that describes existing symptoms, identifies problems, or examines prevailing conditions and practices.

3.3. Research Subjects

The key informants and informants who were the subjects of the research were the village Head, Chair of the Village Consultative Body (BPD), Chair of Community Empowerment Institutions, Chair of Traditional Institutions, Youth Leaders, and Women Leaders.

3.4. Data collection technique

Data collection techniques consist of (1) a Research Library, namely collecting data obtained through books or supporting materials in research; (2). Field Research (Field Work Research) is carried out through observation, interviews, and documentation.

3.5. Data Analysis Techniques

Data analysis was carried out by systematically searching and compiling data obtained from interviews, observations, and documentation. The stages of data analysis are data collection, data reduction, data presentation, and concluding/verification.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. General Description of Research Locations

This research was carried out in Sungai Payang Village, Loa Kulu District, Kutai Kartanegara Regency. Sungai Payang village is just a small, remote village and is filled with very shady forests, a small, very clean water flows, and empties into the Jembayan river, inhabited by two tribes, namely the Lampong tribe and the Basab tribe who first inhabited the interior of the Jembayan river. As time progressed and the number of immigrants who entered this area so that the population increased, this village was opened with a total of 6 hamlets, namely Beroak, Kuntap, Tanah Merah or Lung Anai, Rempanga, Donomulyo and Sentuk. However, in 2003, Tanah Merah Hamlet was expanded and finally became the Lung Anai Cultural Village.

Initially, Sungai Payang Village had a population of only around 30 people with an area of approximately 495,600 m², mostly consisting of the Kutai, Dayak Tunjung/Benuaq, Banjar, and

Javanese tribes. In 2022 the total population of Sungai Payang Village will be 2,946 people, consisting of 1,548 men and women numbered 1,398 people.

Population status based on population levels in 2022, namely: 11 people are illiterate, 13 people are in kindergarten, 71 people have not finished elementary school, 366 people have not finished elementary school, 5 people have not finished junior high school, 149 people have not finished elementary school, and 123 people from Senior High School (Sungai Payang village monograph 2022). Based on the data above, it shows that the low quality of the education level of the population in Sungai Payang Village is inseparable from the limited educational facilities and infrastructure that exist, only in the form of elementary schools, while higher level educational facilities are located in other places which are relatively far away.

Apart from that, other problems are (1) the relatively low economic condition and income of the population; and (2) the problem of health services which are still limited.

General description of the government of Sungai Payang Village, Loa Kulu District, based on Minister of Home Affairs regulations, the leadership structure of Sungai Payang Village, consists of:

1. Village Head
2. Village Secretary
3. Head of Affairs (General and Finance)
4. Head of Section (People's Welfare, Government and Development)
5. Hamlet Head (I, II, III, IV, V and VI)
6. Neighborhood Units I to XIX (Monograph Source Sungai Payang Village, 2022)

In running the government, Sungai Payang Village is assisted, supervised, and controlled by an institution functioning as a legislature, namely the Village Consultative Body (BPD). The institutional and composition of the Village Consultative Body (BPD) consists of:

1. The BPD leadership consists of:
 - a. Chairman;
 - b. Vice Chairman;
 - c. Secretary
2. The fields consist of:
 - a. In the field of Village Government administration and community development; And
 - b. In the field of Village development and empowerment of Village communities

The membership of the BPD consists of BPD members who are representatives of the village population based on regional representation and women's representation which is carried out democratically through a direct election process or representative deliberation, the number of BPD members is at least 5 (five) people and a maximum of 9 (nine) people.

4.2. The role of the Village Consultative Body (BPD)

4.2.1. Role as supervisor of village development

The role of the BPD as supervisor of village development is as a legislative function in carrying out monitoring functions, assessing and correcting the implementation of village development whether it is by previously determined plans and objectives, especially the development of village infrastructure and also non-physical in the village.

Based on the results of an interview with Mr. Arbaen as Head of Sungai Payang Village, the BPD carries out a supervisory role in village development, for example visiting construction sites for roads, bridges, and other aspects as well as conducting interviews with other development

implementing officers, so that development is beneficial for village residents (interview date, May 1, 2023).

Interview with Mr. Hariono Chairman of BPD Sungai Payang Village, said that the role of BPD as supervisor of the development that we carry out is to assess, correct, and ensure conformity between planning documents and implementation realization that are accommodated in APBDes documents including types of activities, sources of funds, the volume of activities and also the budget ceiling. (interview date, May 1, 2023).

An interview with Mr. Samsuriansyah Chair of the LPM (Community Empowerment Institute) of Sungai Payang Village said that the role of the BPD in overseeing village development, such as the process of procuring goods and services as well as supervising infrastructure development such as roads, bridges, buildings and others, is usually the development leader who carries out the supervision. (interview date, May 1, 2023).

Interview with Mr. Yosep, S as Chair of the M. Pekat Traditional Institution, Sungai Payang Village, said that the BPD's role as development supervisor is such as hold consultations in the form of village community meetings regarding village development activities, suggestions, and input for the village development budget. (interview date, May 2, 2023).

An interview with Hilmanus a youth leader, said that the BPD's role as village development supervisor is to control the implementation of development policies, as well as control the use of the development budget, accommodating and channeling the aspirations of village residents. (interview date, May 2, 2023).

Based on the results of interviews and field visits as well as reviewing documents from meetings held by the BPD with the village government, it can be stated that the BPD has carried out its role as a development supervisor with the results of corrections to planning documents and work realization contained in the work handover minutes, for example construction roads, bridges, schools and other non-physical work supported by the BPD also carry out field visits by inspecting them directly while they are carrying out work.

On the other hand, related to the role of the BPD in overseeing village development, is by the authority of the BPD, namely expressing opinions on the administration of Village Government, implementation of Village development, development of Village community, and empowerment of Village communities; and obtaining operational costs for carrying out tasks. and its function in the Village Revenue and Expenditure Budget. To achieve village development goals, the role of the BPD is very important as a control or supervision institution for the implementation of village development and also plays a role as supervisor of village financial management and other functions as stated in the Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia (Permendagri RI) Number 110 of 2016 concerning Village Consultative Bodies (BPD) throughout Indonesia.

4.2.2. Role as Village Head Performance Supervisor

The role of the BPD as supervisor of the performance of the Village Head is to carry out legislative functions, in this case supervising the performance of the executive, namely the village head, in carrying out government and other social tasks.

The results of an interview with Mr. Arbaen the Head of Sungai Payang Village said that his role is that the BPD carries out supervision and asks for official information in the form of an accountability report regarding village government administration that has been carried out and what has not been carried out (interview date, 1 May 2023).

An interview with Mr. Hariono Chairman of the Sungai Payang Village BPD, stated that the role of supervisor of the performance of the BPD village head is always to carry out supervision to encourage and ensure implementation in preparing planning, implementation, reporting stages and

technical progress of the village head must carry out by applicable laws and regulations. (interview date, May 1, 2023).

An interview with Samsuriansyah chairman of the Sungai Payang Village LPM said that in my opinion, the role of the BPD is to create good work coordination between the BPD and the village head to achieve common goals (interview dated, 1 May 2023).

Furthermore, in an interview with Mr. Yosep, S, chairman of the M. Pekat traditional institution, Sungai Payang Village, he said that the BPD's role was to monitor the performance of the village head, saying that the current performance of the village head was good in carrying out village government duties and other community social services. (interview date, May 2, 2023).

The next interview with Mr. Hilmanus as a youth leader said that so far the village head has been able to carry out government activities by the vision, mission, and work programs that have been implemented, although, on the other hand, there are problems and obstacles with the village development budget (interview dated May 2, 2023).

The role of the BPD as a legislative institution to supervise the performance of village heads has been carried out well by the Sungai Payang Village BPD, namely by supervising the performance of the Village Head; evaluating information reports on the implementation of Village Government; holding a special meeting to discuss the performance of the village head and create a harmonious working relationship with the Village Government and other Village institutions.

4.2.3. Role as Village Financial Supervisor

The role of the BPD as village financial supervisor is to assess, correct, and monitor the efficient and effective use of village finances or budgets for the welfare of village residents.

The results of an interview with Mr. Arbaen the Head of Sungai Payang Village said that his role was like deliberating, discussing the BPD with the village government regarding the APBDes. Requesting information regarding the use of the village budget for this year has been carried out. (interview date, May 1, 2023).

Interview Mr. Hariono Chairman of BPD Sungai Payang Village, said that the BPD's role as supervisor of the use of village finances, we always to remind, ensure, and evaluate village financial realization reports whether they are by the plans and provisions for the use of village funds in submitting LKPPD document reports (financial reports accountability for the use of village funds) is submitted every year at the end of the year (interview date, May 1 2023).

An interview with Samsuriansyah chairman of the Sungai Payang Village LPM said that the BPD's role as supervisor of the use of village funds is always to remind them regarding the regulations regarding the use of finance or the village budget as stated in the current APBDes (interview dated, 1 May 2023).

Interview with Mr. Yosep, S as chairman of the traditional institution M. Pekat Sungai Payang Village said that the BPD's role as supervisor of the use of village finances has played a good role, the BPD asks the village head for an LPPD (Accountability Report for the Use of Village Funds) which is routinely made every year. To adjust planning and budget realization for village development. (interview date, May 2, 2023).

A subsequent interview with Mr. Hilmanus as a youth leader said that the BPD's role as supervisor of village finances is to oversee the use of village funds, requesting an accountability report on the use of village funds at the end of each fiscal year in writing to the village head (interview date, 2 May 2023).

The role of the BPD as supervisor of village finances is to ask for information regarding the use of the village budget for this year which has been implemented, namely evaluating the village

financial realization report in the financial report document, accountability for the use of village funds at the end of each year, submitted to the BPD as the citizen legislative body.

4.2.4. Role as a Container & Channeling Aspirations

The role of the BPD as a reservoir and channeling aspirations is to carry out a democratic function, namely accommodating and channeling the aspirations of residents to the Village Government (Village Head) and other related agencies to support village development.

The results of an interview with Mr. Arbaen Head of Sungai Payang Village stated that the BPD as a legislative institution at the village level is obliged to accommodate and channel the aspirations of village residents, including suggestions, input, and criticism as basic capital in making village development a success (interview dated 1 May 2023).

Interview with Mr. Hariono Chairman of the Sungai Payang Village BPD, said that the BPD's role is to accommodate and channel the aspirations of village residents. We at the BPD always explore, accommodate, and channel the aspirations of the residents, this is the main task of the BPD which is carried out by Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia Number 110 of 2014 concerning the Duties of Village Requirements Bodies; namely (a) exploring ideas at the RT, Hamlet & community group level, (b) accommodating and discussing through internal BPD meetings for follow-up to the village government, and (c) channeling community aspirations through village development planning village meetings (interview date, 1 May 2023).

An interview with Samsuriansyah chairman of the Sungai Payang Village LPM said that the BPD's role was to accommodate and channel the aspirations of village residents. The BPD always communicated and coordinated with the village head regarding the aspirations of village residents through village community deliberation forums (interview date, 1 May 2023).

Interview with Mr. Yosep, S as chairman of the traditional institution M. Pekat Sungai Payang Village said that the BPD's role in accommodating and channeling the aspirations of village residents is currently going well, BPD filters and follows up on the aspirations of village residents to the village government, for example proposals for road construction, assistance poor residents, posyandu, cooperation and others (interview date, 2 May 2023).

An interview with Mr. Hilmanus as a youth leader said that the role of the BPD is as a place to accommodate and channel the aspirations of village residents during meetings and deliberations by BPD members, then the BPD secretary reports all aspirations, ideas, notions, and opinions to the village head to be followed up according to the capabilities of the existing resources in our village. . (interview date, May 2, 2023).

Based on the results of interviews and observations, it can be stated that the BPD always strives: (1) to explore ideas at the neighborhood, hamlet, and community group levels; (2) accommodate and discuss aspirations through internal BPD meetings for follow-up to the village government; (3) channeling aspirations through village deliberations for village development planning. Community aspirations are channeled to the village government, such as proposals for road construction, assistance for the poor, posyandu, cooperation, and others.

4.2.5. Role in Proposing Draft Village Regulations

The role of the BPD in proposing draft village regulations is to carry out the legislative function. The village has the right to submit draft regulations or policies to the executive, namely the village head if there is a problem involving many people for the common good.

The results of the interview with Mr. Arbaen Head of Sungai Payang Village said that the BPD submitted a draft village regulation to the village government, then continued with joint discussions between the BPD and the village government. (interview date, May 1, 2023).

Interview with Mr. Hariono Chair of the Sungai Payang Village BPD, said that the role of the BPD may be to draft village regulations through village deliberations. Furthermore. Next is the stage of drafting the village regulation and establishing the village regulation together with the village head as the executive who will implement the village regulation. (interview date, May 1, 2023).

An interview with Samsuriansyah chairman of the Sungai Payang Village LPM said that the BPD's role in submitting draft village regulations is always to coordinate with the village government and adapt to the regulations above. For example, regulations regarding village fund levies, excise, and taxes to fill village treasury (interview date, 1 May 2023).

Interview with Mr. Yosep, S as Chair of the M. Pekat Traditional Institution, Sungai Payang Village, said that the BPD's role in proposing draft village regulations is always to consult with related parties regarding the articles so that they do not conflict with the regulations above or other applicable regulations, for example regarding asset regulations, village inventory items or fund levies carried out by the village government. (interview date, May 2, 2023).

An interview with Mr. Hilmanus as a youth leader said that the BPD's role is to submit draft village regulations, the BPD does not submit draft village regulations regarding RPJMDes and RKPDes, this is the authority that lies above it (interview dated, 2 May 2023).

Based on the results of interviews with respondents and visits to the Sungai Payang Village Office, there are no village regulations made in writing. Regulations are only made based on agreement and volunteering by village residents who still have a high sense of community among the villagers, such as regarding excise levies, taxes, and voluntary donations. The residents' donations are recorded by the village secretary to be included in the village treasury.

In general, the research results show that the duties and roles of the Village Consultative Body in Sei Payang Village as supervisor of village development, supervisor of the performance of the Village Head, supervisor of Village finances, exploring, accommodating, and channeling the aspirations of the village community, and drafting Village Regulations have been carried out well by Law Number 32 of 2004 and Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia Number 110 of 2014 concerning the Duties of Village Requirements Bodies.

4.3. Supporting and Inhibiting Factors of the Role of the BPD

Supporting and inhibiting factors for the role of BPD in carrying out its functions, both internal factors and external factors, are the opinions of several informants, namely as follows:

1. The results of the interview with Mr. Arbaen Head of Sungai Payang Village said that the supporting factors for the BPD's role so far have been quite good quality of human resources, and support for village residents' participation in carrying out village development. Meanwhile, the inhibiting factor, namely the lack of coordination between village institutions and officials, absorbs the aspirations of village residents, and sometimes personal egos and certain groups emerge. (interview date, May 1, 2023).
2. The results of the interview with Mr. Hariono as Chair of the Sungai Payang Village BPD, said that the supporting factors include support for human resource capabilities, supporting infrastructure such as the BPD office and the Permendagri regarding the role and function of the BPD is clear. Meanwhile, the inhibiting factors are the management's education, lack of enthusiasm for work because there is no honorarium, the BPD's inability to understand the duties & position of the BPD, and the village government's inability to understand the function, role & position of the BPD in administering the village government (interview dated May 1, 2023).
3. The results of the interview with Samsuriansyah as chairman of the Sungai Payang Village LPM said that the supporting factors were the availability of regulations regarding BPD and that some BPD members with high school education were able to understand these regulations. Meanwhile,

the inhibiting factor was that the BPD was not in sync with the village government in terms of the village development budget. (interview date, May 1, 2023).

4. The results of the interview with Mr. Yosep, S as chairman of the M. Pekat traditional institution in Sungai Payang Village said that the supporting factors are that the educational level of BPD administrators is quite adequate, with an average high school education, understanding the problems, potential and conditions of the village, and understanding the rules. regulations related to the technical implementation of village administration. Meanwhile, inhibiting factors include, sometimes, the thinking of the BPD and the village government are not in sync with different perceptions and opinions, and some BPD members do not understand the duties and functions of the BPD because they have not read the Home Affairs Regulation. (interview date, May 2, 2023).
5. The results of the interview with Mr. Hilmanus as a youth leader stated that the supporting factors were the creation of collaboration between BPD members and the Village Government which aims to improve the welfare of the people in the Village and the village head provides a BPD office in the Village. Meanwhile, the inhibiting factor is that most BPD members and residents do not understand the function and role of the BPD itself, this is related to the level of education, understanding, and the factor of being busy working to earn a living so that they do not have time to manage the BPD (interview dated, 2 May 2023).

Based on the results of interviews, observations, and document review, the supporting factors for the role of the Sungai Payang Village BPD include: (1) that BPD administrators are on average educated, there is a BPD office available, BPD members understand the problems, potential and conditions of the village, and understand the rules - regulations related to the technical implementation of village administration, the creation of cooperation between BPD members and the Village Government to improve the welfare of the people in the Village.

Factors that hinder the BPD in carrying out its duties include: (1) lack of coordination between village institutions and officials to absorb the aspirations of village residents, sometimes personal egos and certain groups emerge, (2) several members of the BPD management still have junior high school education, (3) some BPD administrators do not fully understand the duties and positions of the BPD, and (4) there is a lack of synchronization between BPD administrators and the village government in terms of the village development budget. This situation is to the results of research by Hidayah and Maros (2019) that the obstacles for BPD in preparing the Village Government Work Plan (RKP Desa) in Teluk Panjang Hamlet, Bathin III District, Bungo Regency are low quality of human resources, relatively low level of welfare, BPD has other jobs, income is less adequate, and the recruitment process. Other research results reported by Ismanudin and Setiawan (2019) show that the obstacles to the BPD's role in village development planning are less effective, including the low quality of human resources (HR) in BPD management, limited resources, both in development planning and implementation. development in the Village, and weak partnership cooperation between the Village Government and the local BPD, as well as less than optimal socialization activities in development planning, both carried out by the District Government and by related Services/Agencies.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The role of the BPD as supervisor of village development, namely studying, assessing correcting, and ensuring conformity between planning documents and the realization of development implementation accommodated in the Village APBD documents. Apart from that, BPD also assesses and corrects the process of procuring goods and services as well as supervising infrastructure development such as roads, bridges, and other buildings in Sungai Payang village.

2. The role of the BPD is to monitor the performance of the village head, for example, the BPD asks for official information in the form of a village head accountability report, encourages and ensures implementation in preparing planning, implementation, reporting stages and technical progress of the village head must carry out by statutory regulations. valid invitation.
3. The role of the BPD as supervisor of village finances, for example asking the village government for information about the use of the village budget every year.
4. The role of the BPD has been to explore ideas at the RT, Hamlet & community group level; Accommodate and discuss through internal BPD meetings for follow-up to the village government.
5. The role of the BPD is to submit draft village regulations to the village government, and then proceed with joint discussions between the BPD and the village government.
6. Supporting factors for the role of the BPD are that BPD administrators are on average educated, the availability of a BPD office, BPD members understand the problems, potential, and conditions of the village, and understand the rules related to the technical implementation of village government, and the creation of good cooperation between BPD and Village Government.
7. Factors inhibiting the tasks and role of BPD are: lack of coordination between institutions and village officials to absorb the aspirations of village residents, sometimes personal egos and certain groups emerge, some BPD administrators have junior high school education, not all BPD members can understand the duties & position of BPD, and there is lack of synchronization between the BPD and the village government in terms of the village development budget.

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